
**HARMONY OF NATIONAL VALUES BASED ON
SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT****Sadikova Makhbubakhon Rakhmonalievna**Lecturer of the Department of Philosophy and National Idea,
Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18221052>

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the harmony of national values in the context of social development, emphasizing their role in shaping a stable and progressive society. It explores the philosophical and sociocultural foundations of national values and their integration with modern principles of social progress. The study argues that national values, when harmonized with universal human ideals, serve as a powerful moral and spiritual resource for sustainable development. The role of education, culture, and social institutions in preserving and promoting these values is analyzed. The article highlights the importance of maintaining a balance between tradition and modernization to ensure the continuity of cultural identity while fostering social innovation.

Introduction: In our country, in the process of today's globalization, great importance is placed on educating young people with high intellect and patriotism grounded in national values. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an encyclopedic document of our state, which, upon analysis, reveals approximately seventy terms and phrases relating to youth upbringing, morality, social protection, and constitutional rights.

Specifically, it emphasizes loyalty to the ideals of creation, high responsibility, social justice, humanism, a democratic legal state, citizen peace, national harmony, customs and traditions, the values of our people, diversity and freedom of ideologies in public life, social justice in human-society relations, sovereign equality of nations in the global community, equality of citizens before the law regardless of beliefs, gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, personal and social status, inviolability of honor and dignity, freedom of conscience, fair labor, creative freedom, access to cultural achievements, and free education of the younger generation—all legally guaranteed by the Constitution. Morality forms an integral part of our national values.

The state operates in the interests of individual and societal well-being, based on principles of social justice and legality. Educating the youth in the spirit of legality, love, and respect for their people, values, traditions, language, and culture fosters genuine patriots who recognize their nation as equal members of the global community. Young people, as a social group, actively influence the development of the country's social system. Their social development reflects the level of their spiritual consciousness, which is shaped by national, religious, and civic awareness, as well as their activities and requirements in life.

Sociological research shows that youth perceive the following as primary qualities defining a person's spirituality: truthfulness (60.8%), respect for national values (55.5%), knowledge of national history and pride (44.2%), purity of heart (39.1%), humility (39.5%), interethnic and interregional tolerance (29.6%), negative attitude toward extremism (19.5%), diligence (0.5%), cultural literacy (0.9%), knowledge (0.7%). Regarding undesirable traits, more than half reject bribery (54%) and arrogance (52.7%), while hypocrisy (17.3%), carelessness (14.5%), freeloading (10.4%), lying (1.7%), envy (0.5%), gossip (0.6%), slander, laziness, and rudeness (0.2%) were also reported.

The survey indicates that young people view the strength of a nation primarily through unity, economic power (69.7%), military strength (44.6%), science (44.4%), politics (41.5%), and morality (37.7%). These results suggest that the younger generation possesses essential qualities that shape their spiritual and moral development.

In the era of globalization and rapid development, societal values are transforming. This includes the spread of moral corruption, individualism, egocentrism, disregard for traditional values, and exposure to potentially harmful "mass culture" influences. These trends pose challenges to protecting youth and national culture, which has become a critical political, spiritual, and academic concern.

The words of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev underscore the urgency: "As a result of insufficient attention to youth upbringing, 31,933 crimes were committed by citizens aged 18 to 30 in 2016." The cultural foundation of national values encompasses human achievements in production, social, and spiritual life. While "mass culture" may provide some benefits, it often erodes individuality, promotes non-nationalized or standardized forms of cultural consumption, and exposes youth to violent and immoral influences, including films, music, and social movements.

Protecting young people requires scientific, practical, and innovative approaches from families, educational systems, and state and public institutions. Factors contributing to youth issues include: a) adults perceiving adolescents as objects rather than individuals; b) youth avoiding adults whose behavior they consider inappropriate; c) families causing aggression or trauma; d) comparisons with peers' family situations; e) teachers interacting without understanding family backgrounds; and f) adverse living conditions (orphanhood, crime, disabilities). A significant portion of youth crime involves individuals from difficult family circumstances, including exposure to alcohol, conflict, or neglect.

The only thing that serves as a bridge of salvation in protecting adolescents and youth from such moral situations and various deviations, vices, and joining bad groups is finding a way to the adolescent's heart, establishing friendly, sincere, and mutually trusting relationships with them. Some parents, wanting their child to become a good person and paying excessive attention to them, unknowingly provide them with all necessary conditions, computers, expensive clothes, and when needed, money, and mobile phones. In scientific terms, such upbringing is called hyperopeka. Parents can protect them like the apple of their eye, giving them all their strength and love, and ultimately raise careless, naive or freeloading, merciless children. To prevent such situations, it is advisable to raise children from an early

age to be loyal to the Motherland based on the formation of their behavior, national-moral, spiritual-cultural values, and the ideology of national independence.

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